

Progress Report on the Publication of the Sirjan material

Work was started on 18th March 1981.

1. Tracings of all extent site plans, trench plans and section drawings were made as they were becoming increasingly worn and faded. Parts of the overall site plan were redrawn from the theodolite readings in the survey notebook. All of these have been inked.
2. The site notebooks were analysed and the stratigraphy interpreted. A précis of the information was made and lists of compatible layers within each trench were drawn up to check with the excavated material.
3. Relevant material from the slide and photographic collections has been sorted out.
4. The excavated material has been separated from the main body of the collection and sorted into trench locations and layers.

The pottery was examined and a type series constructed.

As many sherds were found to join across Williamson's layers, work has been concentrated on reconstructing whole profiles before examining the contents of each layer by type.

About 75% of the pottery remains to be dealt with before a complete type series can be built up and an analysis of the types by contexts be commenced.

The small finds, glass and a quite large collection of stucco from excavation has to be catalogued and drawn or photographed.

Work to be completed.

1. Reconstruction and analysis of remaining pottery.
2. Drawing up for publication of selected vessels, sherds, stucco, glass and small finds.
3. Cataloguing stucco, glass and small finds.
4. Preparation of selected site plans and sections for publication.
5. Written description of excavated features and a summary interpretation of the site plan.

Continued -

Site Survey Material.

This material consists of predominantly ceramic material, with some stucco and glass, collected from various parts of the city itself and the Qalah i Sang.

Whilst many of the types from survey are reflected by the excavated finds, some types are not, although their manufacture at Sirjan is evidenced by kiln wasters.

In some cases the survey material is better preserved than the excavated material and its inclusion within the limits of the current project at some later stage would extend our information of the form and decoration of excavated types.

Work up to date with the excavated material.

Several material from the site and photographs of collections are being sorted.

The excavated material has been separated from the site-plan of the collection and sorted into trench, layers and layers.

The pottery has been sorted and a type series constructed.

The main work has been found to join across the layers. Work has been concentrated on reconstructing whole vessels before examining the contents of each layer by type.

Some 75% of the pottery remains to be dealt with before a complete type series can be built up and an analysis of the types by contents be commenced.

The shell finds, glass and a quite large collection of stucco from excavation has to be catalogued and drawn or photographed.

Work to be completed.

1. Reconstruction and analysis of remaining pottery.
2. Drawing up for publication of selected vessels, sherds, stucco, glass and shell finds.
3. Cataloguing stucco, glass and shell finds.
4. Preparation of selected site plans and sections for publication.
5. Written description of excavated features and a summary interpretation of the site plan.